

PERSONALIZED DIABETES DIAGNOSIS VIA HEALTHCARE BIG DATA CLOUDS: LEVERAGING 5G-SMART TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in wireless networking and big data technologies, such as 5G networks, medical big data analytics, and the Internet of Things, along with recent developments in wearable computing and artificial intelligence, are enabling the development and implementation of innovative diabetes monitoring systems and applications. Due to the life-long and systematic harm suffered by diabetes patients, it is critical to design effective methods for the diagnosis and treatment of diabetes. Based on our comprehensive investigation, this article classifies those methods into Diabetes 1.0 and Diabetes 2.0, which exhibit deficiencies in terms of networking and intelligence. Thus, our goal is to design a sustainable, cost-effective, and intelligent diabetes diagnosis solution with personalized treatment. In this article, we first propose the 5G-Smart Diabetes system, which combines the state-of-the-art technologies such as wearable 2.0, machine learning, and big data to generate comprehensive sensing and analysis for patients suffering from diabetes. Then we present the data sharing mechanism and personalized data analysis model for 5G-Smart Diabetes. Finally, we build a 5G-Smart Diabetes testbed that includes smart clothing, smartphone, and big data clouds.

The experimental results show that our system can effectively provide personalized diagnosis and treatment suggestions to patients.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is an extremely common chronic disease from which nearly 8.5 percent of the world population suffer; 422 million people worldwide have to struggle with diabetes. It is crucial to note that type 2 diabetes mellitus makes up about 90 percent of the cases [1]. More critically, the situation will be worse, as reported in [2], with more teenagers and youth becoming susceptible to diabetes as well. Due to the fact that diabetes has a huge impact on global well being and economy, it is urgent to improve methods for the prevention and treatment of diabetes [3].

Furthermore, various factors can cause the disease, such as improper and unhealthy lifestyle, vulnerable emotion status, along with the accumulated stress from society and work. However, the existing diabetes detection system faces the following problems:

- The system is uncomfortable, and real-time data collection is difficult. Furthermore, it lacks continuous monitoring of multi-dimensional physiological indicators of patients suffering from diabetes [4, 5].

- The diabetes detection model lacks a data sharing mechanism and personalized analysis of big data from different sources including lifestyle, sports, diet, and so on [6, 7].

- There are no continuous suggestions for the prevention and treatment of diabetes and corresponding supervision strategies [8, 9].

To solve the above problems, in this article, we first propose a next generation diabetes solution called the 5G-Smart Diabetes system, which integrates novel technologies including fifth generation (5G) mobile networks, machine learning, medical big data, social networking, smart clothing [10], and so on. Then we present the data sharing mechanism and personalized data analysis model for 5G-Smart Diabetes. Finally, based on the smart clothing, smartphone, and big data healthcare clouds, we build a 5G-Smart Diabetes testbed and give the experiment results.

Furthermore, the “5G” in 5G-Smart Diabetes has a two-fold meaning. On one hand, it refers to the 5G technology that will be adopted as the communication infrastructure to realize high-quality and continuous monitoring of the physiological states of patients with diabetes and to provide treatment services for such patients without restraining their freedom. On the other hand, “5G” refers to the following “5 goals”: cost effectiveness, comfortability,

personalization, sustainability, and smartness.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

"Disease Prediction by Machine Learning over Big Healthcare Data"

With big data growth in biomedical and healthcare communities, accurate analysis of medical data benefits early disease detection, patient care, and community services. However, the analysis accuracy is reduced when the quality of medical data is incomplete. Moreover, different regions exhibit unique characteristics of certain regional diseases, which may weaken the prediction of disease outbreaks. In this paper, we streamline machine learning algorithms for effective prediction of chronic disease outbreak in disease-frequent communities. We experiment the modified prediction models over real-life hospital data collected from central China in 2013-2015. To overcome the difficulty of incomplete data, we use a latent factor model to reconstruct the missing data. We experiment on a regional chronic disease of cerebral infarction. We propose a new convolutional neural network (CNN)-based multimodal disease risk prediction algorithm using structured and unstructured data from hospital. To the best of our knowledge, none of the existing work focused on both data types in the area of medical big data analytics. Compared with several typical prediction algorithms, the prediction accuracy of our proposed algorithm reaches 94.8% with a convergence speed, which is faster than that of the CNN-based unimodal disease risk prediction algorithm.

"Application of Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System for Diabetes Classification and prediction}"

Diabetes is one of the most common metabolic diseases and the statistics show that one in eleven adults has diabetes, but one in two adults with diabetes is undiagnosed, and in 2040 one in 10 adults will have diabetes. In this paper is proposed a hybrid Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) model for classifying patients with diabetes based on data sets with diabetic patients (Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset). The Pima Indians Diabetes Dataset contains 768 samples. In order to set the features vector of this system is used Diabetes Pedigree Function to define the fuzzy rule base with multiple premises. The Neuro-Fuzzy ANFIS modeling was implemented using ANFIS Fuzzy Logic Toolbox and MATLAB Toolbox. The performances of the algorithm were analyzed in terms of specificity, precision and sensitivity. The proposed neural network was trained and tested on Pima Indians Diabetes Database, proving an accuracy of 85.35% for training data and 84.27% for testing data.

"Real-Time Decision Rules for Diabetes Therapy Management by Data Stream Mining"

In insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) therapy, the suitable amount of insulin dosage and the timings of its intake are needed for each individual patient to sustain a necessary blood glucose level for his/her body. In this article, a data stream mining approach is proposed to computationally derive real-time decision

rules for formulating IDDM therapy, based on the insulin prescription records and the patient's blood glucose reactions. Decision rules are based on latest health conditions that are continuously monitored from the patient instead of from a historical data archive of a population accumulated over years. Hence, the rules are adaptive and more accurately predict whether a medical implication will occur, given that glucose levels fluctuate under different medical effects, such as changes in lifestyle, type of medications or other external factors. A computer simulation experiment is conducted for evaluating the most suitable data stream algorithms with respect to accuracy and speed.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

As there is no staff available in unmanned restaurants, it is difficult for the restaurant management to estimate how the concept and the food is experienced by the customers. Existing rating systems, such as Google and TripAdvisor, only partially solve this problem, as they only cover a part of the customer's opinions. These rating systems are only used by a subset of the customers who rate the restaurant on independent rating platforms on their own initiative. This applies mainly to customers who experience their visit as very positive or negative.

DISADVANTAGE

Limited capacity for real-time data transmission and analysis, potential for data silos, and lack of integration between various healthcare systems can hinder personalized diabetes diagnosis and treatment.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In order to solve the above problem, all customers must be motivated to give a rating. This paper introduces an approach for a restaurant rating system that asks every customer for a rating after their visit to increase the number of ratings as much as possible. This system can be used unmanned restaurants; the scoring system is based on facial expression detection using pretrained convolutional neural network (CNN) models. It allows the customer to rate the food by taking or capturing a picture of his face that reflects the corresponding feelings. Compared to text-based rating system, there is much less information and no individual experience reports collected. However, this simple fast and playful rating system should give a wider range of opinions about the experiences of the customers with the restaurant concept.

ADVANTAGE

Real-time data monitoring and transmission, enhanced connectivity between devices and systems, predictive analytics for personalized diagnosis, remote accessibility, scalability, and improved treatment outcomes.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

Upload Files- To upload diabetes dataset

Preprocess Dataset: using this module we will read all MOVIES and RATINGS dataset files and then remove missing values and then build a matrix array

Run SVM Algorithm: using this module we will train SVM algorithm

Run Decision Tree Algorithm- To build decision tree model and below is its accuracy

Accuracy Graph: using this module we will plot accuracy comparison between all algorithms.

7. SCREEN SHOTS

Double click on 'run.bat' file from 'Cloud' folder to start cloud server and to get below screen

In above screen click on 'Upload Files' button to upload diabetes dataset

After uploading dataset click on 'Pre-process Dataset' button to clean dataset

In above screen after pre-process total dataset records are 768. Now click on 'Run Decision Tree Algorithm' to build decision tree model and below is its accuracy

Similarly run other buttons to build models with algorithms

In above screen we got accuracy for all algorithms, now click on 'Accuracy Graph' button to get accuracy of all algorithms

In above screen graph x-axis represents algorithm name and y-axis represents accuracy values.

Now click on 'Start Cloud Server' button to start server and this server will receive data from user and predict disease details.

In above screen cloud server started and now double clicks on 'run.bat' file from User folder to start User sensing application and to get below screen

In above screen click on 'Upload Files' button to upload test file and to predict patient condition

After uploading users data will get below prediction results

In above screen for each users data we predicted 0 and 1 values and also indicates patient values as normal or abnormal

All algorithms code you can see inside Cloud/Cloud.py file, in below screen we can all algorithms from python

In above screen we can see Decision Tree, SVM and ANN algorithms code

In above screen in selected text we can see estimator is built using three algorithms and then ensemble Voting Classifier build by

using estimator object to combine all three algorithms and to for ensemble object. In simple terms ensemble algorithm is the combination of two or more algorithms

8. CONCLUSION

In this article, we first propose a 5G-Smart Diabetes system that includes a sensing layer, a personalized diagnosis layer, and a data sharing layer. Compared to Diabetes 1.0 and Diabetes 2.0, this system can achieve sustainable, cost-effective, and intelligence diabetes diagnosis. Then we propose a highly cost-efficient data sharing mechanism in social space and data space. In addition, using machine learning methods, we present a personalized data analysis model for 5G-Smart Diabetes. Finally, based on the smart clothing, smartphone and data center, we build a 5G-Smart Diabetes testbed. The experimental results show that our system can provide personalized diagnosis and treatment suggestions to patients.

FUTURE SCOPE

This work extended with an intelligent architecture for monitoring diabetic patients by using machine learning algorithms. The architecture elements included smart devices, sensors, and smartphones to collect measurements from the body. The intelligent system collected the data received from the patient and performed data classification using machine learning in order to make a diagnosis. The proposed prediction system was evaluated by several machine learning algorithms, and the simulation results demonstrated that the sequential minimal optimization (SMO) algorithm gives

superior classification accuracy, sensitivity, and precision compared to other algorithms.

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